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Abstract:

The institutional technologies have given them 9a pervasive and elevated status in higher education. However, despite the belief by many that technology can transform teaching and learning, its use is still mainly low-level uploading lecture resources and keeping track of student assignment submissions. In the high-pressured and performance-based university environment, not all lecturers are able to find the time to explore the potential of educational technology to engage students while enhancing learning, assessment of students' work, and evaluation of teaching and courses. The challenges of educational technology use are further compounded by its economic status as a developing country, as well as the "the damaging legacy of colonialism and apartheid" (Grant, 2014, p. 522). This legacy, which threatens to impede the effective and sustainable use of educational technology, is evidenced by poor internet access in some universities, scarce educational technology support expertise, the lofty aspiration to use educational technology to open up access for previously marginalised groups (Ssekakubo, Suleman, & Marsden, 2011) and a lack of an educational technology policy at the national level (Czerniewicz, Ravjee, & Mlitwa, 2006).

Using Technology in Education:

Education "technology," we refer not only to computers but also to a wide range of tools and processes for enhanced learning - including large data systems, audio and video capacity, and online learning. Technology has enabled schools to offer students a variety of experiences that were impossible only a short time ago. Where once we were able to give students access to computers for word processing, basic skill development, and educational games, it is now possible for students to view original historical documents, communicate with experts all over the world, take virtual "field trips," create virtual models to test hypotheses, and much, much more. Teachers, administrators, and parents with Internet access can utilize technologies in a myriad of ways - from immediate access to detailed and manipulate able data on student achievement and demographics, to virtual communities for improving teaching and administrative practices, to daily and direct synchronous interaction (such as instant messaging and videoconferencing) and asynchronous interaction (such as e-mail and newsgroups) between teachers and parents. With recent technology, it now is possible to monitor the achievement and follow the progress of individual students on standardized tests. This form of accountability is popular with policymakers for its straightforwardness and its ostensible equity.

Technology Use in Education:

To understand the scope of the issues around technology and to appreciate the potential impact and value of technology in education, it may be useful to discuss what we mean by education technology use. Presented here are three different frameworks for categorizing technology use proposed by authorities in the field. Each framework sorts technology use differently and offers its own perspective for understanding the influence that technology can have on education.

Enhancing Education through Technology:

- Primary Goal: The primary goal of this part is to improve student academic achievement through the use of technology in elementary schools and secondary schools.
- Additional Goals: The additional goals of this part are the following:
 - To assist every student in crossing the digital divide by ensuring that every student is technologically literate by the time the student finishes the eighth grade, regardless of the student's race, ethnicity, gender, family income, geographic location, or disability.
 - To encourage the effective integration of technology resources and systems with teacher training and curriculum development to establish research-based instructional methods that can be widely implemented as best practices by state educational agencies and local educational agencies.

Improving Learning with Technology has distinguished "five classes of use for information technologies in education that are grounded in the learning sciences":

- Supporting learning in real-world contexts, such as in inquiry projects that allow students to collect scientific data in the national environment.
- Connecting learners to experts and communities of other learners.

- Providing scaffolds and tools to enhance learning, such as visualization and analysis tools that enable students to utilize complex data for higher-order thinking.
- Providing opportunities for feedback, reflection, and revision in the acquisition and construction of knowledge, such as in intelligent tutoring systems.
- Expanding opportunities for teacher learning, using methods such as on-line communities of practice and best-practice case studies. (Pea et al., 2003, p. 4).

Improve Student Learning:

Those requirements are as follows:

- The importance of focusing the use of IT [information technology] on improving the teaching and learning of academic skills, content, and higher order thinking rather than on learning how to use the technology.
- The importance of providing a one-to-one student/computer ratio to enable IT to be fully integrated into teaching and learning.
- The importance of providing reliable and easy-to-use IT that both maximizes the time students can spend using the technology to learn and minimizes the support cost to keep that technology operational.
- The importance of teachers understanding the benefits of fully integrating IT into their work compared with current approaches and tools in the classroom. The most important benefits from embracing the new technologies would be improved student learning and superior work flow management—from standards-based lesson planning and media use, to implementing and supporting student learning activity customized to needs, to assessment and next-step responsive teaching.
- The importance of providing easy ways for teachers to locate appropriate software for IT that provides high-quality learning and teaching.
- The importance of addressing the disconnect in the educational hardware and software markets between the products currently developed and offered by industry and the kind of products that teachers could use effectively to improve student learning. As technology continues to develop, it may become practical and appropriate to develop IT hardware specifically targeted to the need of the education market.
- The importance of addressing IT-related change with systemic approaches that better align and integrate curriculum, instruction and assessment, and appropriate teacher development.
- The importance of investigating the possible use of hardware and software developed for consumer markets, such as cell phones and gaming systems, for supporting learning and education applications as well.
- The importance of exploiting the significant and still unrealized opportunity to employ emerging evidence from the learning sciences to improve the effectiveness of IT applications.
- The importance of defining and investing in long-term research to develop and test new approaches for improving student learning with IT that can be replicated and adapted for use by many student audiences. It is also important to bring them to a scale of use that would benefit students and educators in many more educational environments than happens traditionally by means of government-sponsored research activities. (Pea et al., 2003, pp.7–8).

Integrated System to Student Learning:

The integration of different platforms also provided significant support to student engagement with the textbook and he believes that this contributed significantly to generally good results by forcing students to engage with the textbook material throughout the course, rather than ‘cramming’ just before tests and exams. Besides providing lecturers with a large repository of support material for their lectures and assessments, the integrated environment provided students with many tools to engage with the course material in their textbooks.

Unfortunately, because the video lectures were linked to formative assessment projects which did not carry numerical weighting or incremental deadlines, it led to students postponing their project completion until they were nearing the test. This meant that they came flooding in for help just before the test and were not able to get all the assistance they needed. The results of the test showed that students had barely grasped the “big ideas” that link topics together in the course, and had therefore struggled to decide how best to present and interpret their findings. Earning intervention that utilized multiple technologies to achieve the goal of enriching students’ background knowledge in the subject area. As a collective, these tasks formed what is known as Just-In-Time learning, which allows students to access the resources they need when they need them.

Develop a Shared Teaching, Learning and Technology:

Educational technology visions are often undermined by a failure to develop shared taxonomies, shared technical language, common definitions that further the vision itself, and the policies, plans, implementation strategies and evaluations that follow from the vision. Terms such as “Information and Communications Technologies” have different meanings to different stakeholders. (They even have different meanings to the same stakeholders). Essential instructional constructs, such as “learner-

centered instruction,” are often incompletely or divergently understood by policymakers and teachers. In part, confusion around terminology is due to rapid technological changes. However, a lack of clarity around terminology often reveals a lack of consensus among stakeholders, a failure to think through how and why technology should be used in educational settings, a deeper omission of defining outcomes and impact, and incongruent philosophies of implementation among stakeholders. As a result, profoundly central requisites for effective technology use, concepts like “integration” or “higher-order thinking,” become clichés devoid of real meaning and their implementation uneven or superficial (Burns, 2012).

Part of establishing a common vision around how teachers can teach with technology includes the development of a common language, with shared definitions, standards, levels and outcomes (e.g., through the use of rubrics, matrices or logic maps). By thinking through what terminology means and developing a shared lexicon of terms related to its implementation, educational planners can begin to think in terms of “levels of use” and thus help to further define their vision.

Technology:

Technology is a knowledge aimed at creating tools, action processing and extraction of objects. The term “technology” has been widely recognized and everyone has their own way of understanding the notion of technology. Technology is used to solve problems in our daily lives. Briefly we can describe technology as a product, process, or organization. In addition, technology is used to expand our capabilities, and that makes people as the most important part of any technological system. (Supardan, 2010: 69). Technology is also an application of science to solve problems. But what we must know is that technology and science are different subjects that work hand-to-hand to accomplish a particular task or solve a particular problem. Technology is applied in almost everything we do in our lives; We use technology in the workplace; We use it for extract material; We use technology for communication, transportation, studying, manufacturing, creating tools, securing data, business scale, and more. Technology is a human knowledge involving tools, materials, and systems. Application of technology produces tools or products. If the technology is applied properly, it can be beneficial to humans; but if incorrectly applied, it can cause damage to humans.

Learning Media:

The development of science and technology increasingly encourage renewal efforts in the utilization of technology results in teaching and learning process. Teachers are required to be able to use the tools that can be provided by the school, and it is not possible that the tools are in accordance with the development and demands of the times. Teachers may at least be able to use cheap and humble tools but are required in order to achieve the intended teaching objectives. (Arsyad, 2000: 41)

Besides being able to use the tools available, teachers are also required to be able to develop the available tools; teachers are also required to be able to develop skills to create teaching media that will be used if the media is not yet available.

Learning Media means everything that can be used to stimulate the mind, feelings, attention and ability or skills of learners so as to encourage the learning process. Meanwhile, according to Briggs (1977) learning media is a physical means to deliver content / learning materials such as: books, movies, videos and so forth. Then according to National Education Association (1969) revealed that the media learning is a means of communication in the form of printed media and audio visual, including hardware technology.

Conclusion:

The range of educational technology tools used in the case studies in this publication showcase the variety of teaching and learning activities that can be accomplished using educational technology – from course delivery and student support, to assessment and feedback, and evaluation of teaching and courses. Their integration, however, has to be foregrounded by a critical reflection on the context as well as a discipline specific curriculum (content and pedagogy). This is particularly pertinent if teachers want to move beyond using technology as an appendage or accessory, to selecting the technology based on its suitability for the context and curriculum. My hope is that readers of the case studies in this publication will be challenged to be critically reflective about their use of educational technology and take into consideration not just their contexts and curriculum, but the power dynamics perpetuated by the use of technology in teaching and learning contexts. Technology cannot be separated from our lives in all aspects, including education. Technology in education is very helpful in the process of teaching and learning so that learners are able to obtain all the skills they have to master. It cannot be denied that the role of this technology is very helpful in that regard. Technology is also in line with the development of the era. In the present era, the condition of learners is different from the condition of learners in earlier times, the era before technology was rampant.

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